

Investigation of Total Hip Arthroplasty Performance and The Influence of Their Composition

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ABSTRACT

Hip joint arthritis and failures is a condition that has affected mostly aging population for centuries. This is better understood after looking at the history of artificial hip replacement. The idea of Total hip arthroplasty (THA) was being explored dating back to 1700s.^[1] The first attempt was to improve and smoothen the acetabular head in arthritis cases. Materials such as wooden blocks were placed in the joint with catastrophic results.^[2] In this review, we will explore the main considerations in hip prosthesis. The progress over time to develop better materials and improve the life expectancy of the prosthesis will be discussed. The healthcare cost of replacement combined with aging population requires the orthopedic surgeons looking at proper selection of the prosthesis for the proper indications and selection of the patients. There is no consensus or recommendations for material and design selected for specific patients however better understanding of limitations in material wear and biocompatibility and failure etiologies allows surgeon better serve the patient with correct long-term prosthesis.

Keywords: Total hip replacement; Total hip arthroplasty; Hip joint; Complications; Osteoarthritis; Rheumatoid arthritis; Metal-on-metal; Metal ion release; Ceramic-on-ceramic; Lymphocyte; MOM alloys; Metal-on-metal alloys

INTRODUCTION

The hip joint is an articulation described as a ball-and-socket joint for its extended range of motion.^[3] The spherical femoral head inside of the acetabulum, a lubricated, dome-shaped depression in the pelvic bone, allows for motions including abduction and adduction; flexion and extension; and circular rotations. A capsule around the hip joint is formed by ligaments extending from the lower femoral head to regions around the acetabulum. Articular cartilage rests upon a large, superior, medial surface of the femoral head and the surface of the entire acetabulum. A synovial membrane within the capsule creates a heteropolysaccharide-rich lubricant that reduces most friction between a healthy femoral head and acetabulum. The hip joint is notably more susceptible to dislocation relative to other articulations due to a lack of support structures that inhibit motion.

At present there is approximately more than 300,000 THA procedures performed in the U.S.A. every year.^[4] THA is generally conducted to relieve patients experiencing severe pain in the inguinal region or buttocks associated with osteoarthritis or inflammatory arthritis. Osteoarthritis is a form of arthritis induced by friction of a joint due to physical stress.^[5] Stress may corrode the articular cartilage of the femoral head or acetabulum to induce a non-localizable, dull ache. Rheumatoid arthritis is an autoimmune disease of articulations under pressure. While two-thirds of patients who undergo THA are at least 66 years of age, many youthful patients experiencing juvenile arthritis, an autoimmune disease of the synovial tissue, are recommended the procedure for pain relief. Patients with joint stiffness may be advised to undergo THA, especially if they are bed bound or use walking aids. In general, relief of pain and improvement of motor function are the primary factors of consideration for THA.

Since THA attempts in 1700s, various materials including wood, zinc, glass, wax, silver plates, pumice, resin and ivory were used unsuccessfully to replace the hip joint. It wasn't until 1960s^[6] where THA was performed with better success. Ivory implants were placed with 88% success rate.^[7] Sir John Charnley introduced the concept of Low Friction Arthroplasty using materials such as high-density polyethylene and ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene.^[8] His work led to many long-term successful results.

THA involves four artificial components to replace the hip joint: The acetabular component is a cup-shaped socket that is inserted into a resurfaced acetabulum cleared of damaged articular cartilage and bone.^[9] After removal of the femoral head, an artificial femoral stem is inserted into the remaining femur. A spacer made of either plastic, ceramic, or metal is inserted into the socket of the acetabular component to serve as a gliding surface for the replacement femoral head. The femoral head component attached to the stem can vary in size, depending on the needs of the patient.^[10]

Components of the artificial hip joint selected by a patient and an orthopedic surgeon can vary in composition. Depending on the components selected, durability or longevity of the hip replacement can be prioritized. The femoral and acetabular components can be made from metallic alloys, polyethylene plastic, or ceramic. With the introduction of Metal-on-metal (MOM) THA in 1950s and 60s, it was noticed that the metals used at the time showed significant wear over a year in vivo leading to fractures and failures. Later in recent years the metal ions from the metal wear were seen in blood was concerning for potential toxicity and side effects. Metal-on-metal (MOM) total hip arthroplasty had become the preferred choice for orthopedic surgeons. MOM hip replacements use alloys based on titanium, cobalt, chromium, or other metals.

In the past decade, concerns have grown for patients with MOM hip replacements, especially those with larger femoral heads. Both mechanical wear and corrosion are presumed to increase metal ion concentrations in patients whose THA uses a metal femoral head. MOM hip replacements and others using a metal femoral head have been associated with release of metal ions into the bloodstream of patients.^[11] In 2010, the DePuy ASR Hip Resurfacing System, a MOM articulation, was recalled for its increased risk of wear and accumulation of metal debris. Patients with replacement femoral heads based on cobalt-chromium alloy (CoCr) are reported to have increased levels of cobalt ions and chromium ions in the blood, serum and urine. Elevated cobalt ion concentrations have been directly associated with decreasing overall numbers of T-lymphocytes and B-lymphocytes.^[12] This suggests the immune system is lightly compromised with increased elevation of metal ions. It has also been reported THA patients with

pseudotumors (a condition where increased pressure within the brain often induces brain tumor-like symptoms) have significantly greater concentrations of cobalt and chromium ions relative to asymptomatic patients. There is no evidence of a difference in prevalence of metal allergy between patients using CoCr MOM hip replacements and others using Metal on Porcelain (MOP) articulations, despite the findings of a 10- to 20-fold increase of cobalt and chromium ions within urine samples of the same MOM patients. While most MOM patients are asymptomatic, there is serious concern for a well-defined toxicity threshold for chromium or cobalt ion levels in THA patients.^[13] This threshold could be useful in search of a more suitable MOM design that more effectively balances potential utility and release of metal ions. Other combination of alloys such as Zirconium (Zr) and Vanadium (V) and Tantalum (Ta) in various percentages are being tried to increase biocompatibility and decreased corrosion.^[14] Titanium (Ti) alloys (Beta-Ti) are also being investigated with presence of Molybdenum (Mo) with better module of elasticity relative to bone.^[15]

Other polymer materials such as polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE), high-density polyethylene (HDPE) and ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE).^[16] These materials have been tried in THA as an acetabular piece. The advantage being the great wear resistance and mechanical properties however it has been shown that the wear debris created is very immunogenic and creates significant inflammatory response leading to loosening of the acetabular piece and ultimate failure.^[17] It has also been shown that methods of sterilization using radiation technique oxidized polyethylene and created free radicals that affected the immune reaction. Attempts has been made to cross link and created hybrids with vitamin E to stabilize oxidation after gamma radiation.^[18] This process appears to have helped the oxidation breakdown. Other issues such as fractures on the edges of the prosthetic acetabulum has also been investigated and found to fail if the head of femur placed does have lateral pressure on the edges.^[19]

Finally, ceramics such as Alumina and Zirconia has also been used as a component of Total hips. These materials have great wear resistance, compression performance and minimal biologic reaction however, they as a group have weak tensile strength. Recent development and research have attempted to improve ceramic ability such as BioloxRforte on the market today.^[20] Other combinations of hybrids of alumina and zirconia has also been developed to take advantage of both ceramic quality of compression, wear and tensile strength.^[21]

DISCUSSION

Further research is needed to better understand contributing factors to metal ion release by MOM and other total hip replacement options. Before they were available on the market, MOM articulations using large femoral head sizes were observed to give lower wear and greater function in simulations.^[22] Larger metallic femoral heads however have been observed to increase postoperative failure rates and induce a greater release of metal ions. Some investigations have concluded Pinnacle type modular systems with diameters in the range of 36 to 44 mm provide similar functional enhancement and joint stability to heads at least 48 mm in diameter without a greater release of metal ions into the bloodstream. Metal ion release has been attributed to galvanic corrosion and fretting corrosion, but the overall mechanism for metal ion release at the neck-stem joint is not entirely understood.^[23] Like the

induction of osteoarthritis, general sources of wear, including obesity and intense physical activity, can degrade metallic components of hip replacements, leading to more metal ion accumulation within the body.

Orthopedic researchers are currently optimizing configurations of THA systems made from different materials. In no specific order, some of the choices selected by orthopedic surgeons include metal-on-metal with a smaller femoral head and ceramic-on-ceramic with a larger femoral head and hybrid combinations such as metal on porcelain.^[24,25] Metal-on-metal articulations raise concerns pertaining to an increased wear. The concentration of different ions such as cobalt and chromium ions in patients, which have been linked to compromises on the immune system, brain, and local tissues. MOM total hip arthroplasties were reintroduced in the 1990s for their more extensive longevity relative to other options like MOP. Before, metal-on-polyethylene articulations had decreased in popularity, because polyethylene debris was found to initiate osteolysis, a seriously clinical problem for younger patients. For similar reasons, the more fragile ceramic-on-ceramic total hip replacements are being pushed by researchers. While larger femoral heads have previously been noted for their greater complications in MOM total hip systems, studies have found that larger head sizes for COC hip articulations effectively decrease the rate of postoperative failure relative to both MOM and MOP.

CONCLUSION

Thorough investigation of the different options for total hip arthroplasty is needed to better understand their respective potential for toxicity, corrosion, durability, and other qualities of concern. The FDA continues to approve MOM, MOP, and COC as legitimate options for THA in patients. Prospective studies are necessary to give doctors algorithms in matching appropriate prostheses to patients' needs and functions. An example is a lack of literature that investigates the optimal THA for malnourished patients. While much of orthopedic literature focuses on normal weight or obese patients, less interest is expressed for the higher rates of postoperative complications in malnourished THA patients.^[26] It is also essential that prospective documentation of all hip prosthesis placed and progress, prognosis and failures documented. This allows the surgeons better select the hip implant appropriate for each patient and address individualized needs.

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